

Synthesis in the Pyrazolone Series. Action of Semi- and Thiosemi-carbazides on Ketonic Esters.

Part III.

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In previous communications (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3, 80; 1928, 5, 459) of this series it has been shown by one of us that thiosemicarbazide and semicarbazide condense with β -ketonic esters to form pyrazolone derivatives with carbothioamide and carbonamide groupings as substituents and that they have different degrees of stability. In Part II it has been shown that the behaviour of these carbazides towards benzoylacetic ester and diacetosuccinic ester differs from that of acetoacetic ester inasmuch as, instead of yielding the intermediate carbazones, they produce at once the pyrazolone compounds.

The object of the present investigation is to study the action of semi- and thiosemi-carbazides on the various substitution products of acetoacetic ester, namely, methylacetoacetic ester, ethylacetoacetic ester, dimethylacetoacetic ester, oxalacetic ester, benzoylacetoacetic ester, acetylacetoacetic ester and acetosuccinic ester; and it has now been found that the carbazides yield with the methyl-, ethyl- and dimethyl-acetoacetic esters pyrazolone compounds free from the carbothioamide or carbonamide group, due evidently to the looseness with which such groups are attached to the nucleus.

With the exception of methylacetoacetic ester the other esters show no tendency to unite with the carbazides at the ordinary temperature. From this ester and semicarbazide two products are formed (*vide* Experimental), and of these the lower melting substance is either a semicarbazone (I) or a pyrazolone carbonamide, (II) and the higher melting one is 3:4-dimethylpyrazolone:

(I)

With thiosemicarbazide methylacetoacetic ester gives a thiosemicarbazone which is relatively stable in warm water or alcohol but in boiling water is transformed into 3:4-dimethylpyrazolone which is derived evidently from the pyrazolone carbothioamide, first formed during the process. Thiosemicarbazide and semicarbazide give with dimethylacetoacetic ester the same compound, *vis.*, 4:4'-dimethylpyrazolone. Ethylacetoacetic ester yields with semicarbazide two products, *vis.*, 3-methyl-4-ethylpyrazolone-1-carbonamide and 3-methyl-4-ethylpyrazolone. This latter compound is also formed with thiosemicarbazide.

Oxalacetic ester reacts with semicarbazide in the usual manner to yield pyrazolone-3-carboxylic ester derived from pyrazolone-1-carbonamide-3-carboxylic ester first formed by the elimination of the carbonamide group.

Along with pyrazolonecarboxylic ester another compound possessing the empirical formula, $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{N}_5$ has also been isolated the formation of which can be easily explained by supposing that semicarbazide acts upon the carboxylic ester group of either (IV) or (V) and the compound (VI or VII) so obtained then parts with a molecule of water and yields a compound (either VIII or X) or

(IX or XI) of which the former loses the carbonamide group and gives rise to the latter.

Acetosuccinic ester gives with semicarbazide a mixture of two products which are separable by means of boiling water, one being completely insoluble and the other soluble. The insoluble product melts at 225° and gives on analysis a very high percentage of nitrogen. The constitution of this compound has not yet been determined. The nature of the reaction and the composition of this will be described in a subsequent communication. The water-soluble product melts at 220° and has the composition, $C_8H_{13}O_3N_2$. The formation of this substance can be illustrated by either of the following schemes :

The compound (XIII) has been obtained by Curtius (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1894, 50, 517) from hydrazine hydrate and acetylsuccinic ester. But as the compound obtained by us is different, it must have the alternative formula (XV).

Both the carbazides yield with benzoylacetoacetic ester the same compound 3-phenyl-5-methylpyrazole-4-carboxylic ester (XVII), the formation of which can be represented thus:

But by condensation of acetylacetoacetic ester with semicarbazide two products are formed, *vis.*, 3:5-dimethylpyrazole-4-carboxylic ester (m.p. 96°) (XXII) and 3-methylpyrazolone (m.p. 215°) (XX). The same ester gives with thiosemicarbazide two products, one of which (m.p. 96°) is identical with 3:5-dimethylpyrazole-4-carboxylic ester and the other is 3-methylpyrazolone-1-carbothioamide (m.p. 180°) (XIX).

The formation of these products indicates that acetylacetoacetic ester behaves both as a β -keto ester and as a β -diketone. As a β -diketone it condenses with the carbazides to form a pyrazole (XXI) from which the compound (XXII) is derived. As a β -keto ester it yields the pyrazole derivatives (XVIII) from which the acetyl

group is probably eliminated giving the compound (XIX) and from this the compound (XX).

EXPERIMENTAL.

3:4-Dimethylpyrazolone (III).—Methylacetoacetic ester (1 mol.) dissolved in alcohol was added to an aqueous solution of semicarbazide hydrochloride (1 mol.) and sodium acetate (1 mol.). The mixture was allowed to stand overnight when only a small quantity of a solid product separated. After two days a further quantity of a solid crystalline product melting between 180° and 262° was obtained. It was dissolved in warm alcohol and the alcoholic solution fractionally precipitated with water, but these different fractions had the same melting point as the mother-substance. The mixture was then boiled with water for 3—4 hours with animal charcoal. From the filtrate a crystalline precipitate was obtained which melted at 262° with previous shrinkage at 249°. The melting

point remained unchanged even when it was crystallised four times from water. This substance was 3:4-dimethylpyrazolone. (Found: N, 25.12; $C_7H_8ON_2$ requires N, 25.00 per cent.).

The same compound was obtained much more easily by heating an aqueous-alcoholic solution of the components for about two hours. The pyrazolone so obtained is insoluble in ether, chloroform and benzene; easily soluble in warm alcohol and in boiling water. This compound has also been prepared by Rothenburg (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1895, 52, 40) who obtained it from (i) 3-methylpyrazolone and methyl iodide, and (ii) from methylacetoacetic ester and hydrazine hydrate and gave the melting point as 249°. But by repeating his experiments the compound prepared by the latter method shrank at 249° and melted at 262°, and the compound from the former method melted at 249°. From this it appears that the two compounds are isomeric. That obtained from hydrazine hydrate and methylacetoacetic ester is 3:4-dimethyl-pyrazolone and the other is 1:3-dimethyl-pyrazolone.

Methylacetoacetic Ester Thiosemicarbazone.—When an aqueous solution of thiosemicarbazide hydrochloride (1 mol.) was shaken up with methylacetoacetic ester (1 mol.) in presence of sodium acetate, the thiosemicarbazone gradually separated out. The white precipitate mixed with some of the unchanged ester was decanted from the mother-liquor, washed with water and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 192°. (Found: N, 19.42. $C_8H_{15}O_2N_3S$ requires N, 19.85 per cent.). When this thiosemicarbazone was boiled with water or when the reaction was carried out in boiling aqueous solution 3:4-dimethylpyrazolone was obtained.

3:4:4'-Trimethylpyrazolone.—A solution of semicarbazide hydrochloride (1 mol.) and sodium acetate (1 mol.) dissolved in the minimum quantity of water was poured into an alcoholic solution of dimethylacetoacetic ester. The mixture after being vigorously shaken for 3—4 hours was allowed to stand for two days with frequent shaking. As no solid separated out and the ester remained unchanged as an emulsion, the mixture was boiled for five to six hours when a clear solution was obtained which on cooling gave a crystalline solid. This was crystallised from water with the addition of animal charcoal, m.p. 262°-263°. (Found: N, 22.39. $C_8H_{10}ON_2$ requires N, 22.22 per cent.). The same compound was obtained with thiosemicarbazide.

3-Methyl-4-ethylpyrazolone.—Equal quantities of ethylacetoacetic ester, semicarbazide hydrochloride and sodium acetate were

heated in aqueous-alcoholic solution on the water-bath. Before all the ester (which was undissolved to begin with) went into solution, a white crystalline precipitate separated out after about 10 minutes and within a short time the reaction flask was filled with a voluminous flocculent precipitate. Heating was then continued for 20 minutes more, the solid was boiled with alcohol when a portion went into solution. From the filtrate, on cooling, a white light crystalline substance (m.p. 226°) was obtained and was found to be identical with 3-methyl-4-ethylpyrazolone of Rothenburg derived from hydrazine hydrate and ethylacetoacetic ester. (Found: N, 22.43. $C_6H_{10}ON_2$ requires N, 22.22 per cent.)

The same compound was obtained by heating an aqueous solution of thiosemicarbazide hydrochloride, sodium acetate and ethylacetoacetic ester for two to three hours.

3-Methyl-4-ethylpyrazolone-1-carbonamide.—The alcohol insoluble product in the above experiment consisted of white crystals, m.p. 259° (sharp). When this was boiled with water it gradually went into solution which on cooling gave 3-methyl-4-ethylpyrazolone, m.p. 226° (confirmed also by mixed melting point). As the substance could not be crystallised undecomposed and gave a very sharp melting point it was analysed. (Found: N, 24.62. $C_7H_{11}O_2N_3$ requires N, 24.85 per cent.)

3-(5-Keto-1:2:4-triazole)-pyrazolone (IX or XI).—This compound was obtained by heating a mixture of semicarbazide hydrochloride, oxalacetic ester and sodium acetate in molecular proportion in dilute alcoholic solution. After heating the mixture for 3–4 hours a white crystalline solid was obtained which could not be crystallised from any solvent; m.p. 265° (sharp). (Found: N, 42.10. $C_5H_5O_2N_5$ requires N, 41.90 per cent.)

Pyrazolone-3-carboxylic Ester (V).—The solution from the previous experiment gave on cooling a solid product which was dissolved in absolute alcohol and precipitated by ether as white needles, m.p. 178° . (Found: N, 17.84. $C_8H_8O_3N_2$ requires N, 17.04 per cent.)

3-Phenyl-5-methylpyrazole-4-carboxylic Ester (XVII).—To the alcoholic solution of benzoylacetoacetic ester (1 mol.) was added an aqueous solution of semicarbazide hydrochloride (1 mol.) and sodium acetate (1 mol.) and the mixture was heated for an hour. The precipitate was crystallised from water in white rectangular plates, m.p. 282° . The same compound was also obtained

when the semicarbazide was replaced by thiosemicarbazide. (Found: N, 12·36. $C_{13}H_{14}O_2N_2$ requires N, 12·17 per cent.).

3:5-Dimethylpyrazole-4-carboxylic Ester (XXII).—When a mixture of acetylacetoacetic ester (1 mol.) with an aqueous solution of semicarbazide hydrochloride and sodium acetate was heated for about an hour a semi-solid mass was obtained which became crystalline on long standing. When this solid was shaken up with ether a portion went into solution. The ether-insoluble product crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 215° and was identical with 3-methylpyrazolone. The solid obtained from the ethereal solution crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 96°, and was 3:5-dimethylpyrazole-4-carboxylic ester. (Found: N, 16·85. $C_8H_{12}O_2N_2$ requires N, 16·66 per cent.).

Two compounds were also obtained when the above experiment was repeated with thiosemicarbazide. But in this case 3-methylpyrazolone 1-carbothioamide (m.p. 180°) was formed together with the product melting at 96°, the method of separation and isolation being the same in both cases.

3-Methyl-2-keto-tetrahydro-pyridazine-4-carboxylic Ester (XV).—An alcoholic solution of acetoacetic ester (1 mol.) was added to an aqueous solution of semicarbazide hydrochloride (1 mol.) and sodium acetate. After heating the mixture for about 5 minutes white crystals began to separate out, heating being continued for nearly an hour. A portion of the precipitate on being boiled with water went into solution and gave on cooling a white crystalline precipitate, m.p. 220°. (Found: N, 15·00. $C_8H_{12}O_3N_2$ requires N, 15·22 per cent.).

The water-insoluble part consisted of white crystals which could not be crystallised from any ordinary organic solvent; m.p. 258° (decomp.).

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